

1 Analysis of GPU Memory Allocation Characteristics

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11 Abstract

12 The number of applications subject to safety-critical regulations is on the rise, and consequently,
13 the computing requirements for such applications are increasing as well. This trend has led to the
14 integration of General-Purpose Graphics Processing Units (GPGPUs) into these systems. However,
15 the inherent characteristics of GPGPUs, including their black-box nature, dynamic allocation
16 mechanisms, and frequent use of pointers, present challenges in certifying these applications for
17 safety-critical systems.

18 This paper aims to shed light on the unique characteristics of GPU programs and how they impact
19 the certification process. To achieve this goal, several allocation methods are rigorously evaluated to
20 determine which one is best suited to an application, regarding the program characteristics within
21 the safety-critical domain.

22 By conducting this evaluation, we seek to provide insights into the complexities of GPU memory
23 accesses and its compatibility with safety-critical requirements. The ultimate objective is to offer
24 recommendations on the most appropriate allocation method based on the unique needs of each
25 application, thus contributing to the safe and reliable integration of GPGPUs into safety-critical
26 systems.

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32 **Supplementary Material** The full set experiment results (data and garphics)

33 *Dataset (Experiment results):* <https://github.com/marcosrc92/MARS-data>

34 1 Introduction

35 Safety-critical systems have long been integral to various sectors, including aviation, nuclear
36 power generation, healthcare, and more. In today's world, these systems are even more
37 prevalent in our daily lives with the development of autonomous systems. Therefore, it
38 is crucial to ensure that the development and deployment prioritise safety and adhere to
39 rigorous standards to protect occupants, pedestrians, and workers on industrial environments.

40 High Performance Computing (HPC) platforms are those which are designed to accelerate
41 data processing to solve complex and computationally intensive problems, some architectures
42 include the use of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), Field-Programmable Gate Arrays

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43 (FPGAs) or Tensor Processing Units (TPUs). These accelerators are increasingly establishing
44 their presence on these sectors by delivering accelerated computations within real-time
45 constraints. However, these heterogeneous systems have inherent limitations, with GPU
46 schedulers exhibiting a black-box behaviour. Additionally, a well-known issue is the bottleneck
47 that arises in the data transfer process between the host system (CPU side) and the device
48 (accelerator side), leading to unpredictable data access times. Over the years, independent
49 authors and companies have dedicated their efforts to develop memory allocation algorithms
50 and architectures specifically aimed at achieving faster data accessing and deterministic
51 behaviour of GPUs.

52 To ensure the reliability and uniformity of outcomes, this paper conducts an evaluation of
53 various allocation methods using the Rodinia benchmark suite [10, 11, 18, 1]. The assessment
54 encompasses both static and dynamic attributes extracted from the benchmarks, employing
55 tools offered by NVIDIA and other contributors. Static metrics, such as data size, the
56 number of allocations, copies, kernel launches, cache hit rate, and memory coalescence, are
57 taken into account. Moreover, the dynamic aspects inherent in any code, such as allocation,
58 data copying, kernel launching API usage, and overall execution time, are meticulously
59 documented to discern potential connections with the static ones.

60 A significant enhancement to the benchmark analysis includes a desirable feature for
61 safety-critical systems, the ability to control the timing of memory allocations. Leveraging
62 the *XeroZero* a tool introduced by [8], that allows that the entire memory allocation
63 is executed only once and exclusively at the beginning of the execution for the NVIDIA
64 allocation methods, we were able to achieve that behaviour. That tool has support to
65 create this memory pool using Unified Memory (UM) and zero-copy (ZC). In this work, we
66 add support to the traditional allocation method to grant an equal comparison between all
67 results gathered from each memory configuration. Our analysis aims to provide conclusions
68 regarding the most suitable allocation method based on the identified program characteristics,
69 regarding mean measurements for those metrics to reveal the swiftest method, reinforced
70 with assessments of standard deviation and histogram representations to gauge predictability,
71 thereby providing valuable insights for informed decision-making.

72 The organisation of this paper is as follows: Section 2 introduces the most relevant
73 previous works that inspired this study. Section 3 presents the memory managing methods
74 that have been selected to conduct the time analysis on memory accesses that is presented in
75 this work. Section 4 describes *XeroZero* highlighting our modifications. Section 5 describes
76 the static characteristics and dynamic metrics used for evaluating how they are related and
77 affect the timing response. Section 6 exposes the data treatment, the value extracted from
78 executing every benchmark with different memory configuration and a comparative analysis
79 extracted from the results. Finally, Section 7 summarises the most important ideas and
80 outline future work to be undertaken.

81 **2 Related Work**

82 In this section we present the prior work in the field, aiming to contextualise our research,
83 identify gaps, and build on established frameworks. We identify two categories of memory
84 management, a) studies which aim into new allocation strategies and b) studies which extract
85 conclusions from reverse engineering the GPU. Our work is influenced by two streams: studies
86 focused on new allocation strategies and those aimed at understanding memory through
87 reverse engineering. We employ these techniques to get metrics, using tools designed to alter
88 memory behaviour, to highlight which characteristics are relevant during program execution.

89 2.1 Allocation strategies

90 A. Calderón introduces a tool named *XeroZerox*, which is specifically designed for embedded
91 platforms [8]. This open source tool carries out a two-phase analysis and modification process
92 on the source code. In the first phase, it intercepts explicit GPU memory allocation calls and
93 copies creating a mapping between CPU and GPU variables. In the second phase, leveraging
94 this information, it strategically replaces the allocation method sections, opting for UM or
95 ZC allocation instead of the default GPU memory allocation method. *XeroZerox* also creates
96 a pool of memory to allocate all the data at once at the beginning of the process and free
97 it at the end, being a desirable behaviour for safety-critical applications, first for avoiding
98 the timing overhead and non-time deterministic nature of the memory allocations which can
99 impact the worst case execution time of the program, as well as to ensure that the size of the
100 memory allocations is fixed, and therefore can always be satisfied at program deployment.

101 Another strategy is proposed by Sven Widmer et al. [22]. They developed an allocator
102 focused on enhancing SIMD scalability for small, frequent memory allocations, minimising
103 branch divergence. The system-wide default allocator performs well with few simultaneous
104 requests, and this approach optimises data accesses by utilising one superblock shared
105 among warp threads. A voting mechanism selects a worker thread, reducing simultaneous
106 memory requests and invocations. This design eliminates the need for superblock header
107 data, streamlining memory allocation and minimising synchronisation and memory overhead.
108 Aggregating memory requests within a warp ensures efficient cache utilisation, aligning with
109 the goal of minimising the use of the default allocator for improved performance.

110 Another approach is described by Andrew Adinetz [3]. HALloc is a statically sized
111 memory pool, which is subdivided into chunks during initialization, while the handling of
112 large allocations relies on the CUDA dynamic memory allocator. For each allocation size,
113 only one active bin from which to allocate is kept by HALloc. When a configurable threshold
114 for usage within a bin is reached, it is replaced with a new active bin, maximizing the chances
115 of subsequent allocations finding an available block in the active bin. Lists of bins that
116 are almost-exhausted and almost-empty are also kept by HALloc for each size. Bins are
117 moved between these two lists during free operations, and bins in the almost-empty list
118 are used to select new active bins when needed. Per-size bins are also maintained by their
119 fine-grained allocator, but a linked list is used to track all active bins, avoiding costly active
120 bin replacement operations.

121 Zaid Qureshi et al. [19] develop the BaM System (Big accelerator Memory). This tool
122 allows programmers to access big data sets which exceed the GPU memory available in the
123 system, by accessing data stored in storage devices in an on-demand and fine-grained manner,
124 while improving the access time. The authors call this “accelerator-centric” architecture.
125 Threads on GPU can bring data wherever it is stored, either on CPU or any other storage
126 system. This reduces the use of page-faulting mechanism from CPU and it is demonstrated
127 using NVMe SSDs.

128 In terms of predictability, Björn Forsberg et al. [14] show how to enhance cache hit rate
129 through the adept management of prefetching and evicting using Predictable Execution
130 Models (PREM). To enhance predictability, they introduce a division into a memory phase
131 and a compute phase, a strategy akin to that of *XeroZerox*. They leverage a “replacement
132 policy” that “selects which data to evict when new data is requested”.

133 2.2 Reverse engineering

134 On reverse engineering, Jake Choi et al. [13] performed a comparative analysis between
 135 UM and ZC in relation to the traditional *cudaMalloc* over a NVIDIA Jetson TX2 SoC, an
 136 embedded platform based on Pascal architecture. By evaluating those allocators against
 137 three benchmarks of the Rodinia suite, they extract and compare metrics such as memory
 138 usage and execution time. Their study concludes that the traditional method should not be
 139 the default choice for programmers. In fact, the optimal allocator depends on the specific
 140 application being considered.

141 Calderón et al. [6] created a tool for the reverse engineering of the default CUDA memory
 142 allocator in terms of functionality and timing behaviour. They showed that similar to CPU
 143 allocators, the CUDA allocator works with power of two bin sizes and that GPU memory
 144 allocations which fall into a newly allocated or reallocated bin affects the execution time
 145 of the subsequent GPU kernel call. Their open source tool is able to extract the bin sizes
 146 and memory pools of NVIDIA GPUs and has been demonstrated with both desktop and
 147 embedded GPUs. Moreover, later the tool was extended to OpenCL and non-NVIDIA
 148 GPUs [7].

149 3 Allocation Methods

150 Over time, there has been a concerted effort from both industry players and academic
 151 researchers to devise quicker algorithms, all with the common goal of enhancing data access.
 152 In the following we provide a succinct overview of the algorithms under evaluation. It's
 153 worth noting that these particular algorithms were selected for their seamless integration and
 154 straightforward implementation on our embedded GPU platform i.e. open source availability
 155 of their code and compatibility with embedded NVIDIA GPUs. Interestingly, the first three
 156 algorithms hail from the research and development efforts of NVIDIA, while the fourth stems
 157 from an independent researchers' work.

158 **CUDA traditional allocation** is the native allocator of CUDA C programming language
 159 [12]. It is used through *cudaMalloc*, which allocates device global memory of a specified size.
 160 The operating system looks for space in the memory pool using one of the following policies:
 161 first-fit, best-fit, worst-fit or next-fit. Still, data movements must be explicitly done using
 162 *cudaMemcpy*.

163 **Zero-Copy**. In order to transfer data from host (CPU) to device (GPU) or in the
 164 reverse direction, the memory has to be copied to a page-locked buffer. This process can be
 165 avoided by allocating paged-locked (also known as pinned memory) with *cudaMallocHost*
 166 or *cudaHostAlloc* calls, so data can be directly accessed by the device using DMA (Direct
 167 Memory Access). Enabled by Unified Virtual Addressing (UVA) released on CUDA 4, it
 168 makes data accessible through PCI-e avoiding *cudaMemcpy* calls.

169 **Unified Memory**. Supported since CUDA 6, this allocation method [15] joins both
 170 Central Processing Unit (CPU) and GPU memory address spaces in a single one. Using
 171 *cudaMallocManaged* function, data is allocated into that space, returning a pointer accessible
 172 both from host and device. Similar to ZC there is no need of explicit copy declaration because
 173 the system migrates data automatically.

174 **ScatterAlloc**. This algorithm [21] organises a memory pool into a structure called *Super*
 175 *Block*. This structure has a fixed size of memory that is also split into equal size pages. Its
 176 author also proposes a method to keep track of free memory in two levels of hierarchy. At
 177 higher level a *Page usage table* is used that stores which pages are in use and freed. At lower
 178 level, inside each page, there is another table which keeps track of chunks within a page.

179 In order to make allocations faster, the algorithm changes the storing region when 90% of
180 the pages are filled. In addition, the author introduces an approach to reduce simultaneous
181 access from different threads to the same memory region.

182 **4 Memory analysis and reconfiguration**

183 To introduce a safety framework and enable consistent comparisons between allocation
184 methods, this work uses the *XeroZerox* tool [8] developed by A. J. Calderón mentioned in
185 Section 2, extended with support to traditional memory allocation to fit the needs of our
186 analysis. This tool offers numerous benefits: it allows us to modify memory models without
187 altering the original benchmark code. Additionally, it supports the use of a single, preallocated
188 memory pool at the program start-up. This is a highly desirable feature for safety-critical
189 systems, as it enables control over memory reservation and the ability to calculate the worst
190 case execution time of this process. In the utilisation of the *XeroZerox* tool for assessing
191 allocation methods, a critical observation emerges: the original tool initially overlooked the
192 case of the traditional allocation model. This discrepancy poses a substantial challenge to
193 achieving a comprehensive comparison among allocation strategies. In this work we address
194 this issue in order to perform a fair comparison. Next, we delineate our methodology for
195 utilising the *XeroZerox* tool and address the gap it initially presents concerning the traditional
196 allocation model. To enhance a robust comparison between allocation methods, we have
197 devised an approach to incorporate this gap within our analysis framework.

198 *XeroZerox* analyses GPU applications and determines the size of a centralised memory
199 pool that can serve all its needs. This pool is allocated at the beginning of the application
200 using zero-copy or unified memory allocation and it is released upon its completion. Serving
201 as a sub-allocator, *XeroZerox* intercepts traditional memory allocations and substitutes them
202 with allocations served consecutively – i.e. similar to a bump allocator – from the centralised
203 memory pool, with minimal and constant runtime cost. This approach accommodates legacy
204 GPU applications within critical setups’ memory management constraints, without any code
205 modifications. Moreover, *XeroZerox* prioritises minimising memory consumption, effectively
206 reducing both the memory footprint and the runtime overhead associated with memory
207 management for these applications.

208 To intercept the target memory functions, the analysis library employs a technique
209 referred to in the literature as *interposition* [9]. This method involves substituting the target
210 functions with user-defined wrapper functions. These wrappers serve to augment the original
211 functions with additional functionality, such as extracting information from their arguments,
212 which is particularly pertinent to our objectives. The analysis library is executed only the
213 first time of executing the application and generates a comprehensive report including details
214 like the maximum memory utilisation, the count of memory pool instances generated, the
215 frequency of memory transfers and the detection of any memory leaks. On a second phase,
216 which is the only one used for subsequent executions, eg. at deployment, once the centralised
217 memory pool is established in the initialisation of the GPU application, *XeroZerox* assumes
218 the role of a sub-allocator, handling allocation requests from the application in accordance
219 with the matches loaded from the optimisation profile. Notably, *XeroZerox* adopts a strategy
220 where it fulfils memory allocation requests solely for the initial request it receives. Subsequent
221 allocation requests prompt *XeroZerox* to return a pointer to the memory region already
222 allocated for the preceding request, effectively optimising memory utilisation by reusing
223 allocated space. This approach minimises redundant allocations and contributes to more
224 efficient memory management within the application.

■ **Figure 1** XeroZero tool behaviour

225 In this paper, we extended *XeroZero* with support for the traditional allocation method.
 226 We took advantage from the analysis phase, to identify the CUDA calls. At this point,
 227 instead of creating just one memory pool to be allocated using ZC (Zero Copy) or UM
 228 (Unified Memory) method at the beginning of the optimisation phase, host and device pools
 229 are created separately as it is performed when the default CUDA allocation method is used.
 230 During an allocation call, the tool discerns whether it is a GPU or CPU allocation, storing
 231 the data in the corresponding pool through a linked list. Additionally, the incorporation of
 232 support for copy calls has been essential due to the existence of two distinct allocated pools.
 233 This ensures that whenever such a call is activated, the tool can reference the variables to
 234 the pre-allocated pools, facilitating the migration of data.

235 As illustrated in Figure 1, the dark blue boxes denote components of the original *XeroZero*
 236 tool, representing the baseline framework. Whereas, the yellow boxes highlight additional
 237 elements we added to ensure a fair comparison among different allocation methods.

238 **5** Benchmark's characterisation

239 The Rodinia benchmark suite is a collection of parallel applications designed to evaluate the
 240 performance and scalability of computer systems, particularly those with multicore processors
 241 or GPU accelerators. It was developed by researchers at the University of Virginia as a
 242 resource for evaluating and comparing different parallel computing architectures.

243 This benchmarking suite is one of the most widely used GPU benchmarking suites used in
 244 the literature. Since our purpose is to analyse the general memory allocation behaviour of

GPU software and find out the optimal memory allocation method for use in safety critical systems, we intentionally avoid using a GPU benchmarking suite targeting explicitly safety critical systems like GPU4S Bench and OBPMark, which have a predictable, easy to analyse memory allocation behaviour, similar to the one achieved by *XeroZero*.

Rodinia contains 23 benchmarks, characterised by their computation patterns, named *Dwarfs* by Paul Springer [20] and introduced by Asanovic et al. [4]. They refer to recurring structures or strategies used to solve problems and perform tasks in computational systems. These patterns provide standardized ways to approach common computational problems, making it easier to design, implement, and understand. Despite their utility in classification, our analysis indicates that these patterns do not have any relevance on our results. Furthermore, during the execution of 13 out of 23 Rodinia benchmarks, runtime errors or system crashes were encountered, causing the hardware to reboot. To maintain the integrity of the results, we opted not to modify the benchmark code to force compatibility with the ARM-based embedded system used. Those evaluated are presented in Table 1 along with the name of the benchmark and the data loaded is provided by Rodinia’s developers.

■ **Table 1** Evaluated Rodinia benchmarks

Applications	Dwarfs	Datasets
Back Propagation	Unstructured Grid (UG)	65536 elements
Gaussian Elimination	Dense Linear Algebra (DLA)	3x3 matrix and 1024x1024 matrix
LU Decomposition	Dense Linear Algebra (DLA)	64x64 matrix and 2048x2048 matrix
Kmeans	Dense Linear Algebra (DLA)	100 and 819200 elements x 34 columns
Breadth-First Search	Graph Traversal (GT)	1 million nodes and 4096 nodes
SRAD_v1	Structured Grid (SG)	512x512 image
Hotspot	Structured Grid (SG)	Two square matrices of 64x64, 512x512 and 1024x1024 each
Heart Wall	Structured Grid (SG)	104 frames: 609x590 pixels
Leukocyte	Structured Grid (SG)	600 frames: 640x480 pixels
Myocyte	Structured Grid (SG)	16 parameters 1 instance 100 ms

Taking into consideration prior research, we have curated a set of characteristics that define a program for our experimental setup, categorized into static and dynamic metrics. Static metrics provide intrinsic insights into program structure, encompassing cache hit rates, shared memory usage, coalescence, memory access frequency, and data transfer sizes between CPU and GPU. On the other hand, dynamic metrics focus on timing operations, including overall program execution time, kernel execution time, CUDA APIs execution time, and memory operations execution time. This comprehensive approach enables a thorough evaluation of program performance across various dimensions, facilitating informed comparisons between different allocation methods and program configurations. Crossing results from both categories is the key to obtain conclusions of how program characteristics influence its timing results. The following subsections give a deeper understanding of these categories.

5.1 Static metrics

These metrics provide intrinsic insights into program structure, highlighting how a program is coded and its inherent characteristics. These metrics are crucial for understanding the efficiency and resource usage of a program. The following points explain each static metric in detail:

- 1. Cache Hit Rates:** This metric assesses the efficiency of data retrieval from cache memory. A high cache hit rate indicates that most data requests are satisfied by the

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279 cache, leading to faster data access and improved performance. Analysing cache hit rates
280 helps in optimizing memory hierarchy and reducing latency.

281 **2. Shared Memory Usage:** This metric evaluates the utilization of shared memory
282 resources within the system. Efficient use of shared memory can reduce global memory
283 accesses and increase the speed of data processing. Understanding shared memory usage
284 is key to optimizing memory allocation and parallel processing capabilities.

285 **3. Coalescence:** This metric examines the degree to which memory accesses are coalesced,
286 which optimizes data transfer efficiency by grouping multiple memory requests into a single
287 transaction. High coalescence reduces the number of memory transactions, improving
288 bandwidth utilization and reducing latency.

289 **4. Memory Access Frequency:** This metric quantifies the frequency of memory accesses,
290 indicating the demand for data retrieval during program execution. High memory
291 access frequency can highlight potential bottlenecks and guide optimizations to minimize
292 redundant memory operations and enhance overall performance.

293 **5. Data Transfer Sizes Between CPU and GPU:** This metric measures the volume of
294 data exchanged between the central processing unit (CPU) and the graphics processing unit
295 (GPU). Large data transfers can introduce significant overhead and latency. Understanding
296 and optimizing data transfer sizes are crucial for improving inter-device communication
297 and overall program efficiency.

298 5.2 Dynamic metrics

299 On the other hand, dynamic metrics focus on timing operations, providing insights into
300 various aspects of program execution. The following points explain each dynamic metric in
301 detail:

302 **1. Overall Program Execution Time:** This metric captures the total duration from the
303 start to the end of the program's execution.

304 **2. Kernel Execution Time:** This metric measures the time taken to execute computational
305 kernels, which represent the core processing tasks of the program. Analysing kernel
306 execution time helps in understanding the efficiency of the computational workload and
307 identifying areas for optimisation within the kernels.

308 **3. CUDA APIs Execution Time:** This metric examines the time spent executing CUDA
309 Application Programming Interface (API) calls. These calls manage GPU resources and
310 operations, so their execution time reflects the overhead associated with GPU management.
311 Specifically, this includes the time taken for kernel launches, memory allocations, data
312 transfers, and, in some cases, synchronization operations.

313 **4. Memory Operations Execution Time:** This metric measures the duration required
314 for memory read and write operations. It is indicative of data transfer efficiency and
315 memory access latency. Optimizing memory operations execution time can significantly
316 enhance overall program performance, particularly in data-intensive applications.

317 6 Experimental Results

318 In this section, we present the results of testing various allocators on the Rodinia benchmark
319 suite using their standard input set. Subsequently, in the following sections of this section,
320 graphical representations of the data are provided to facilitate a time comparison between
321 the selected allocators for each metric across all benchmarks. This analysis examines the

322 performance characteristics, strengths, and weaknesses of each allocator in relation to the
 323 benchmarks' nature.

324 Due to the extensive volume of collected data, we have opted to store it in a dedicated
 325 GitHub repository [2]. Detailed information from each of the 500 iterations, as well as
 326 summarised characteristics in Excel files, can be accessed through this repository. This
 327 approach allows for transparency and facilitates access to the comprehensive dataset for
 328 those interested in further analysis or replication of the study.

329 6.1 Experimental setup

330 For each allocation method outlined in section 3, we performed multiple iterations of each
 331 benchmark on an NVIDIA Jetson Orin AGX, an embedded GPU platform certified for use in
 332 the automotive sector. Due to the inherent variability in GPU execution times, as discussed
 333 in section 5, each benchmark was executed 500 times with the same data inputs. This number
 334 of runs allows for a reliable calculation of the mean and standard deviation for each selected
 335 parameter, ensuring statistically meaningful results. The variability in execution times was
 336 verified through time histograms, which support the assumption of a Gaussian distribution.
 337 These histograms are available for review on our GitHub repository [2]. In contrast, obtaining
 338 static metrics was more straightforward, as these remain consistent regardless of when the
 339 data collection tool was launched or the memory configuration selected.

340 Only memory access methods interacting with *XeroZerox* have been studied, using the
 341 unmodified benchmarks as baseline. This approach was chosen due to a key feature of
 342 *XeroZerox* that aligns it with safety-critical systems: memory allocation is managed by
 343 ensuring that all allocations occur at the start of the execution.

344 Using the *NVIDIA NSight Systems* and *NVIDIA NSight Compute* tools alongside each
 345 benchmark, we generated a timing report containing dynamic metrics and a characterization
 346 report featuring static metrics. The benchmarks from Rodinia were compiled using CUDA
 347 version 11.4 and automated with Python scripts version 3.8.10. Metric extraction was
 348 performed using *NVIDIA NSight Systems* version 2022.4.2.1 and *NVIDIA NSight Compute*
 349 version 2023.2.0.0 build 32895467.

■ **Figure 2** Metrics extracted for every evaluated benchmark.

350 **6.2 Profiling**

351 The initial set of static characteristics was extracted from the profiling tool *NVIDIA NSight*
 352 *Systems*, and the results are presented in Table 2. This table displays basic static charac-
 353 teristics, such as the number of allocations and deallocations performed using *cudaMalloc*
 354 and *cudaFree*, the number of copies made by *cudaMemcpy*, the quantity of kernels launched,
 355 and the size of the data moved. The data related to other native allocation instructions,
 356 like *cudaBindTexture* or *cudaMemcpyToSymbol*, has been retained in its original form. This
 357 decision is grounded in the belief that these instructions offer essential functionality required
 358 by programmers. To aid interpretation, certain cells in the table have been colour-coded
 359 and star-marked: blue cells (*) are the value believed to be the edge on the allocator choice,
 360 while a green background (**) represent values that exceeded the threshold established for
 361 influencing allocator selection, this is founded on the conclusions presented in the following
 362 subsection.

363 During our work, the necessity of acquiring a deeper understanding of the behaviour of each
 364 benchmark was recognised. For this reason, we have made use of *NVIDIA NSight Compute*
 365 to acquire a second set of static metrics related to kernels. To make sure that the allocation
 366 method does not interfere with these results by comparing the kernels’ characteristics, binaries
 367 run from a clean build and from binaries interfered with *XeroZerox*, which are shown in
 368 Table 3. In three benchmarks (*gaussian* with 1024 size matrix, *srad_v1* and *myocyte*) the
 369 NVIDIA’s tool could not complete the analysis. For these two cases the report was empty
 370 despite how many times we run the test. We suspect that this might be due to the high
 371 number of kernels launched, due to this limitation we could not provide information about
 372 these tests.

373 We observed an anomalous L2 cache hit rate for kernel 2 in the *leukocyte* benchmark,
 374 consistently reported by the *NVIDIA NSight Compute* tool, despite multiple reruns of the
 375 benchmark. Since we lack access to the internal workings of this tool, we are unable to
 376 provide a definitive explanation for this irregularity.

377 At the core of our analysis lies a meticulous process of data collection of the dynamic
 378 metrics during each iteration of the benchmarking procedure. This data, intricately tied to
 379 the associated process and variable, serves as the foundation for subsequent calculations of
 380 mean and standard deviation. An example of results from those executions is illustrated in
 381 Figure 3 for API’s executions and in Figure 4 for memory and kernel operations.

382 Figure 3 represents a benchmark with a specific input set size. Vertical axis (y) represents

■ **Figure 3** APIs-hotspot 64x64 matrix

■ **Figure 4** Mem/Kernel Ops-hotspot 64x64

■ **Table 2** Benchmark Characteristics

Dwarf	Benchmark	Data	Allocations	Copies	Kernels launched	Data sizes
DLA	Gaussian	Matrix 3x3	3	6	4	$\leq 64kB$
		Matrix 1024x1024	3	6	2046 **	4 MB, $\leq 64kB$ *
	LUD	Matrix 64x64	1	2	10	$\leq 64kB$
		Matrix 2048x2048	1	2	382 **	16,777 MB **
	Kmeans	List 100x34 elements	4	7	3	$\leq 64kB$
List 819200x34 elements		4	7	3	11.4 MB, 3,277 MB **	
SG	srad_v1	512x512 image	12	206 **	502 **	0.920 MB , $\leq 64kB$
	hotspot	Two squared matrix 64x64	3	3	1	$\leq 64kB$
		Two squared matrix 512x512	3	3	1	1.049 MB
		Two squared matrix 1024x1024	3	3	1	4.149 MB *
	heartwall	104 frames: 609x590 pixels	623	50	20	1.952 MB , $\leq 64kB$
	leukocyte	600 frames: 640x480 pixels	34	39	7	0.561 MB , 0.472 MB , $\leq 64kB$
	myocyte	16 parameters 1 instance 100 ms	4	16500 **	3900 **	$\leq 64kB$
UG	backpropagation	65536 elements	6	8	2	4.457 MB , 0.262 MB , $\leq 64kB$ *
GT	BFS	4096 nodes	7	23	16	98 kB , $\leq 64kB$
		1 million nodes	7	31	24	24 MB , 8 MB , 4 MB , 1 MB , $\leq 64kB$ **

383 the normalised time consumed on running every API taking as baseline benchmarks without
 384 being modified with a value of 1.00, called *traditional alloc* at the picture. The x axis
 385 represents each allocation method evaluated, from left to right: traditional alloc, traditional
 386 *cudaMalloc* with XeroZero optimisation, *ScatterAlloc*, *ZC* with XeroZero optimisation and
 387 *UM* with XeroZero optimisation. The z axis represents every API call considered relevant,
 388 from front to rear: Kernel launch time, allocation API (every method has its own), copy API,
 389 synchronisation API (not every benchmark uses this instruction) and overall execution time.

390 On the other hand, Figure 4 illustrates kernel and memory operations execution times.
 391 Similar to the representation used in the APIs figures, these figure differ in that one of the
 392 horizontal axes has been adjusted to show which operations are being evaluated. Each kernel
 393 call and the normalised time it takes to transfer data from the CPU to the GPU and vice
 394 versa are depicted, using the traditional allocation method as a baseline with a value of
 395 1.00. For *UM* and *ZC*, the transfer time is not included due to the unique behaviour of these
 396 methods, as explained in Section 3.

397 Complete information is contained in a Github repository [2], where Excel documents
 398 contain detailed information of the mean and standard deviation arranged in folders ordered
 399 by DWARFS alongside with 3D chart representations to condense data.

400 6.3 Comparative Analysis

401 In this subsection we discuss the results extracted from the correlation between static and
 402 temporal analysis, taking two distinct scenarios. The first revolves around an analysis just
 403 concerning the overall execution time. In contrast, the second is oriented to those systems
 404 characterised by continuous operation, like safety-critical systems responsible for monitoring
 405 the environment from startup to the moment the machine is shutdown. These systems
 406 typically entail a single allocation at initialisation, followed by recurrent data movement and

■ **Table 3** Kernels Characteristics

Dwarf	Benchmark	Data	L1 cache hit rate	L2 cache hit rate	Coalescent memory	Excessive sectors accessed
DLA	Gaussian	Matrix 3x3	kernel 1: 33,33% kernel 2: 60%	kernel 1: 56,77% kernel 2: 66,47%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	kernel 1: no kernel 2: 2 (20%)
		Matrix 1024x1024	no data	no data	no data	no data
	LUD	Matrix 64x64	kernel 1: 48,39% kernel 2: 39,24% kernel 3: 25%	kernel 1: 40,51% kernel 2: 42,87% kernel 3: 61,14%	Uncoalesced Shared Accesses	kernel 1: 562 (41%) kernel 2: 6216 (70%) kernel 3: no
		Matrix 2048x2048	kernel 1: 48,39% kernel 2: 58,22% kernel 3: 53,29%	kernel 1: 40,51% kernel 2: 49,38% kernel 3: 64,42%	Uncoalesced Shared Accesses	kernel 1: 562 (41%) kernel 2: 263144 (70%) ker- nel 3: no
	Kmeans	List 100x34 elements	kernel 1: 82,08% kernel 2: 86,49%	kernel 1: 54,79% kernel 2: 27,73%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	kernel 1: 3009 (70%) kernel 2: no
		List 819200x34 elements	kernel 1: 52,78% kernel 2: 41,07%	kernel 1: 71,98% kernel 2: 67,62%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	kernel 1: 24371200 (78%) kernel 2: no
SG	srad_v1	512x512 image	no data	no data	no data	no data
	hotspot	Two squared matrix 64x64	16,13%	62,54%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	864 (27%)
		Two squared matrix 512x512	4,65%	68,69%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	67192 (31%)
		Two squared matrix 1024x1024	3,54%	68,67%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	273184 (31%)
	heartwall	104 frames: 609x590 pixels	95,48%	97,14%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	9958 (19%)
	leukocyte	600 frames: 640x480 pixels	kernel 1: 99,23% kernel 2: 98,78% kernel 3: \approx 98%	kernel 1: 22,51% kernel 2: 172,91% kernel 3: \approx 80%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses	kernel 1: 3051 (19%) kernel 2: 122584 (88%) ker- nel 3: \approx 580000 (18%)
	myocyte	16 parameters 1 instance 100 ms	no data	no data	no data	no data
UG	backprop	65536 elements	kernel 1: 58,30% kernel 2: 71,18%	kernel 1: 52,52% kernel 2: 54,17%	Uncoalesced Global Accesses in both kernels	kernel 1: 73728 (18%) kernel 2: 163847 (15%)
GT	BFS	4096 nodes	kernel 1: 19,40% kernel 2: 7,19%	kernel 1: 50,19% kernel 2: 49,48%	No coalescence warning	
		1 million nodes	kernel 1: 0,04% kernel 2: 0,01%	kernel 1: 0,91% kernel 2: 0,93%	No coalescence warning	

407 kernel launches throughout operation, culminating in memory deallocation upon shutdown.

408 6.3.1 Analysis regarding overall execution time

409 By correlating static results (explained in section 5) and dynamic results from the time
410 analysis, we derived programming guidelines for GPU usage, presenting distinct conclusions
411 based on overall execution time and considerations more pertinent to safety-critical systems.
412 Generally speaking, the traditional method with the *XeroZerox* optimisation out stands
413 over the other allocation methods regarding the total execution time of the benchmark.
414 Additionally, there are other characteristics that had been seen relevant to choose a method
415 of memory management. It appears that the most relevant one is the cache hit rate. This
416 can be observed in the cases of both the *heartwall* and *leukocyte* benchmarks, where the hit
417 rates for both L1 and L2 caches exceed 90%. In such cases, the traditional allocation method
418 without optimisation yields the lowest overall execution times.

419 In general, when a substantial number of kernels is launched, and some data involved in
420 copies that exceed 4 MB, the zero-copy method with *XeroZerox* proves to be the optimal
421 allocation method, resulting in the lowest overall execution times. Conversely, when the
422 number of copies and kernel launches is small, and the data copied does not exceed 4 MB,

423 both zero-copy and unified memory yield similar results, with unified memory demonstrating
424 the lowest execution times for sizes below that threshold.

425 There are, however, exceptions. For instance, the *BFS* benchmark should have a clear
426 allocator preference. When using 4096 nodes, unified memory is preferred, while when
427 loading 1 million nodes, zero-copy performs better. Remarkably, the execution times are
428 very similar for both allocators, with the size having only a minor impact. This benchmark
429 is unique in that it exhibits coalescent memory, thereby minimising excessive sector accesses,
430 which could explain the observed behaviour.

431 Given these observations, benchmarks such as *gaussian* (loading a 3x3 matrix), *LUD*
432 (loading a 64x64 matrix), *kmeans* (loading 100x34 elements), and *hotspot* (loading a 64x64
433 matrix) were expected to behave similarly. However, temporal results reveal that *hotspot* and
434 *LUD* perform better with unified memory, while *kmeans* and *gaussian* yield better overall
435 execution times with zero-copy. It was found that the first couple make use of shared memory
436 and experience a higher number of warps stalled compared to the latter two benchmarks.

437 Below, observations are presented concerning overall execution time, categorized by
438 their respective levels of importance, with the highest level of importance listed first. Each
439 observation is paired with a recommended allocator:

- 440 1. L1 and L2 cache hit exceed 90% -> traditional allocation method
- 441 2. Coalescent memory -> zero-copy + XeroZerox or Unified Memory + XeroZerox
- 442 3. When a substantial number of kernels (measured at 2 in blue or green) are launched &
443 data size greater or equal than 4 MB -> zero-copy + XeroZerox
- 444 4. When number of kernels launched is small & data size less or equal than 4 MB -> Unified
445 Memory + XeroZerox
- 446 5. Use of shared memory -> Unified Memory + XeroZerox
- 447 6. High number of warps stalled -> zero-copy + XeroZerox

448 6.3.2 Analysis regarding kernels and copies execution times

449 Another interpretation of the results can be made if the programmer is looking to adapt
450 the code into safety-critical systems. One important recommendation is to perform memory
451 allocations only once at the beginning, a behaviour achieved automatically with the *XeroZerox*
452 optimisation. Moreover, memory freeing is not a relevant characteristic in this case, because
453 the expected execution is that the system runs continuously, reading and writing data,
454 moving it between CPU and GPU and executing functions and kernels. So considered metrics
455 here are the time that the copy and kernel launch APIs are active, and the kernel and copy
456 execution times.

457 Upon examining the active time of the copy API and the kernel launch API, it's observed
458 that **conventional method without XeroZerox intervention and ScatterAlloc**
459 typically emerge as the faster options. However, there are instances where other methods
460 yield similar times. The observed behaviour aligns closely with the previous findings, with
461 one notable exception found in the *backpropagation* benchmark. Here, both ZC and UM
462 methods show comparable performance to the traditional method.

463 When looking at copying operations, the first thing noticed is that there is no data when
464 using ZC or UM, presumably because there is no explicit copy between CPU and GPU, so
465 the delay depends on the related API. On the other cases, the time grows proportionally
466 with the size copied being in any case in the same magnitude order, no special correlation is
467 found here.

468 To verify the accuracy of the mean and standard deviation as appropriate measures,
469 histograms were generated for each process, also available on the mentioned GitHub repository [2].
470 Notably, the traditional allocation method exhibited considerable variation in results,
471 suggesting a lack of consistency. As a result, **it is advisable to avoid the traditional**
472 **allocation method** in systems targeting safety-critical or real-time scheduling, regardless
473 of the mean results. Also when employing the traditional allocation method in any form, the
474 histograms for copying and allocating APIs exhibited a multi-modal distribution, while ZC
475 and UM usually exhibit one gaussian bell shape, so in terms of predictability it is advised to
476 use these last two methods in case that *ScatterAlloc* is not the preferable method.

477 **7 Conclusion**

478 In this work, we analysed the dynamic memory behaviour of GPU programs for safety critical
479 systems, targeting the widely used suite GPU benchmark suite, Rodinia. Studying all this
480 data has revealed some reasons behind the allocator's behaviour have been identified through
481 a static analysis of the benchmarks.

482 The specific characteristics and requirements of each benchmark and kernel influence
483 the choice of GPU memory allocation method. Factors such as cache hit rates, data sizes,
484 and the number of kernel launches may play a crucial role in determining which allocation
485 method is the most suitable for a given scenario.

486 For future research and validation of the conclusions presented in this work, the following
487 avenues can be explored:

- 488 1. Microbenchmarks for Specific Scenarios: Conducting microbenchmarks designed to test
489 each specific scenario and characteristic identified in this research can provide a more
490 detailed and comprehensive validation of the conclusions. This can help in fine-tuning
491 allocation methods for precise use cases.
- 492 2. GPU Direct RDMA [16] and GPUDirect Storage [17]: Investigating the use of NVIDIA's
493 GPUDirect RDMA and GPUDirect Storage methods represents a promising direction.
494 These technologies facilitate direct GPU access to data stored in storage units such as
495 SSDs, circumventing CPU involvement. This approach holds the potential to deliver
496 substantial performance benefits and minimize latency in data-intensive applications.
497 The work of J. Bakita et al.[5] is directly relevant to this topic and can be utilised to
498 propel advancements in this area.
- 499 3. Evaluation on other platforms: Consider how these allocation methods perform on
500 different GPU architectures and platforms, as compatibility and performance can vary.

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